

Blue emissive Zn^{II} sensor by N₄O₃ heptadentate ligand in mixed aqueous solution at physiological pH 7.4[†]

Amar Hens and Kajal Krishna Rajak*

Inorganic Chemistry Section, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : kajalrajak@hotmail.com

Abstract : The N₄O₃ coordinating heptadentate ligand forms a dinuclear zinc complex 1·H₂O·ClO₄, [Zn₂L·2H₂O]·H₂O·ClO₄. In the complex, two zinc ions are held together by a μ-phenoxo bridge where the geometry around the Zn1 atom is distorted trigonal bipyramidal ($\tau = 0.75$) and that of Zn2 is intermediate between square based pyramid and distorted trigonal bipyramid ($\tau = 0.43$). The complex is highly fluorescent in the solution phase as well as in solid state. The emission intensity of the complex in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4 is ~150 times more than H₃L ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 285 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 330 \text{ nm}$, $\Phi_{\text{F}} = 0.399$).

Keywords : Zinc(II), pH, heptadentate ligand, emission.

Introduction

In the field of coordination chemistry, the progress in synthetic receptors for cation has attracted considerable attention in recent decades due to the fact that a large number of biological processes involve molecular recognition of cationic species. It is thus important to develop techniques for quantifying or sensing such cation. The importance of zinc ion in the biological domain primarily lies in the fact that it is an essential trace element acting as a structural component of proteins and peptides. Search for reagents which can efficiently act as fluorescence sensors for Zn²⁺ has been an active area of research¹⁻³. Its role in the catalytic site of enzymes is also well-known⁴.

The common probes are aryl sulfonamide derivatives of 8-aminoquinoline, such as 6-methoxy-(8-*p*-toluenesulfonamido)quinoline (TSQ)⁵ and Zinquin, as well as Zinbo-5⁶, the Zinpyr (ZP) family⁷⁻⁹, and the ZnAF molecules¹⁰ all of which contain highly conjugated system and are almost insoluble in desired solvent. Here, we introduce a simple and well yield dinuclear Zn²⁺ complex containing hepta dentate chelating ligand and all the photophysical properties of this complex are investigated under 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4 at 25 °C. The luminescent property in the working buffer shows that the emission intensity of H₃L increases sig-

nificantly (~ 150 times) upon addition of various concentrations of Zn²⁺, while the introduction of other transition metal ions and biologically relevant metal ions (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺) causes the intensity to be either unchanged or weakened. The system shows selective chelation enhanced fluorescence (CHEF) in the presence of Zn²⁺ ion. It is to be noted that Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ exhibit similar kind of fluorescence properties with different fluorescent sensors¹¹. Therefore, it is necessary to develop Zn²⁺-selective sensors that can make a distinction of Zn²⁺ from Cd²⁺ with high sensitivity and selectivity.

Experimental

Materials :

All the starting chemicals were analytically pure and used without further purification.

Caution! Perchlorate salts are highly explosive, and should be handled with care and in small amounts.

Physical measurements :

UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer LAMBDA 25 spectrophotometer. Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) measurements were done on a Micromass Qtof YA 263 mass spectrometer using acetonitrile as a solvent. The molar conductivity was deter-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

mined using Systronics Conductivity Meter 304 in acetonitrile solution at room temperature. Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were performed on Perkin-Elmer 2400 series II analyzer. The emission data were collected on a Perkin-Elmer LS 55 fluorescence spectrometer. Quantum yields of the complexes were determined in freeze-pump-thaw-degassed solutions of the complexes by a relative method using quinine sulfate solvent as the standard. The fluorescence decay data were collected on a Hamamatsu MCP photomultiplier (R3809) and were analyzed by using IBH DAS6 software.

Computational details :

The geometrical structure of the complex **1** [**Zn₂L·2H₂O**] was optimized by the DFT¹² method with B3LYP exchange correlation functional¹³ approach. The geometry of the complex was fully optimized in solution phase without any symmetry constraints. The vibrational frequency calculation was also performed for the complex to ensure that the optimized geometry represents the local minima and there are only positive eigen values. On the basis of the optimized ground state geometry structure, the absorption spectra property in methanol was calculated by time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT)¹⁴ approach associated with the conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)¹⁵. We computed the lowest 40 singlet – singlet transition. The effective core potential (ECP) approximation of Hay and Wadt was used for describing the (1s²2s²2p⁶) core electron for zinc whereas the associated “double- ξ ” quality basis set LANL2DZ was used for the valence shell¹⁶. For H atoms, we used 6-31+G basis set and for C, N and O atoms, we employed 6-31+G* as basis set to optimize the ground state geometry. The Figures are showing in MOs, NTOs and the difference density plots were prepared by using the GaussView 5.1 software. All the calculations were performed with the Gaussian 09W software package¹⁷. GaussSum 2.1 program¹⁸ was used to calculate the molecular orbital contributions from groups or atoms.

Crystallographic studies :

The single crystal suitable for X-ray crystallographic analysis of the complex **1·H₂O·ClO₄**, [**Zn₂L·2H₂O**]**·H₂O·ClO₄** was obtained by slow evaporation of aqua-methanolic solution. The X-ray intensity data were col-

lected on Bruker AXS SMART APEX CCD diffractometer (Mo K α , $\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 293 K. The detector was placed at a distance 6.03 cm from the crystal. Total 606 frames were collected with a scan width of 0.3° in different settings of ϕ . The data were reduced in SAINTPLUS¹⁹ and empirical absorption correction was applied using the SADABS package¹⁹. Metal atom was located by Patterson method and the rest of the non-hydrogen atoms emerged from successive Fourier synthesis. The structure was refined by full matrix least-square procedure on F^2 . All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. All calculations were performed using the SHELXTL V 6.14 program package²⁰. Molecular structure plots were drawn using the ORTEP^{21a} and Mercury^{21b} softwares. Relevant crystal data are given in Table 1.

Synthesis of complex :

1·H₂O·ClO₄, [**Zn₂L·2H₂O**]**·H₂O·ClO₄** An aqueous solution of Zn(ClO₄) \cdot 6H₂O (0.230 g, 0.60 mM) was added to a methanolic solution of H₃L (0.150 g, 0.29 mM) and the reaction mixture was warmed in water bath with care. A dilute methanolic solution of Et₃N (0.090 g, 0.90 mM)

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement parameters for [**Zn₂L·2H₂O**]**·H₂O·ClO₄**

	1·H₂O·ClO₄
Formula	C ₃₁ H ₄₇ ClN ₄ O ₁₀ Zn ₂
M_r	801.96
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P21/c
a (Å)	12.599(4)
b (Å)	24.548(7)
c (Å)	12.890(4)
α (°)	90
β (°)	115.528(2)
γ (°)	90
V (Å ³)	3597.7(2)
Z	4
D_{calcd} (mg m ⁻³)	1.473
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.466
θ (°)	1.7–27.5
T (K)	293(2)
Reflections collected	8253
$R1^a$, $wR2^b$ [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.058, 0.150
GOF on F^2	1.008
$^aR1 = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $. $^b wR2 = [\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum [w(F_o^2)^2]]^{1/2}$	

was then added to the reaction mixture to maintain at a pH of 7–8; then refluxed for 2 h with afforded air and was allowed to cool to room temperature. The reaction mixture was then filtered, and the volume of solvent was reduced via rotary evaporator to obtain a white residue. The residue was filtered and washed by methanol and was then dried in vacuum. Colorless single crystals suitable for diffraction were obtained from water-methanol (1 : 4) mixture. Yield : 0.210 g (88%). Elemental Anal. Calcd. for C₃₁H₄₇ClN₄O₁₀Zn₂ : C, 46.43; H, 5.91; N, 6.99. Found : C, 46.39; H, 5.92; N, 7.01; ¹H NMR { δ (ppm) ar = aromatic, Me (N) = amine- methyl, Me (C) = aromatic- methyl, Bz =benzyl, My = methylene} : 7.41 (H10, ar), 7.22 (H2, ar), 7.19 (H3, ar), 7.01 (H4, ar), 3.88 (H7, Bz), 3.8 (H10, Bz), 2.75 (H8, My), 2.55 (H9, My), 2.33 (H27, Me(N)) and 2.19 (H29, Me(C)); ESI-MS (CH₃CN) : *m/z* Calcd. 647.1730, Found : 647.1784 (100%); Molar conductance, Λ_M : (CH₃CN solution) 126 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The heptadentate symmetrical N₄O₃ ligand H₃L was made to react with Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O in a ratio of 1 : 2 in methanol and water mixture at room temperature in air to produce complex of composition [Zn₂L·2H₂O]·H₂O·ClO₄

in excellent yield as a form of colorless crystalline solid. The synthetic procedure of the ligand and the efficiency of the formation of binuclear complexes were reported in our previous work²². The details data for ESI-MS and NMR spectra are given in Experimental section.

Crystal structure of [Zn₂L·2H₂O]·H₂O·ClO₄ :

The asymmetric unit of complex **1**·H₂O·ClO₄ contains one L³⁻, two Zn²⁺ ions, three water molecules and one perchlorate anion (Fig. 1a). The geometry around the Zn1 atom is distorted trigonal bipyramidal ($\tau = 0.75$) whereas that of Zn2 is intermediate between square based pyramid and distorted trigonal bipyramid ($\tau = 0.43$)²³. The binuclear core comprises of two zinc atom bridged equatorially by endogenous cresolate group.

The equatorial positions at Zn1 are occupied by O1 and O2 atoms of phenoxo group, N2 atom of amine group and the axial positions are occupied by N1 of atom of amine and O4 of the coordinated water molecule respectively. Similarly the equatorial base of Zn2 is formed by O2, O3 and N4 atoms and the axial positions are occupied by N3 and O5 atoms. Both zinc centers are surrounded by pentacoordinated identical environment of N₂O₃ donor in which the Zn-O and Zn-N bond distances vary between 1.968(3)–2.121(5) Å and 2.113(4)–2.131(4) Å, respectively (Table 2). The axial angle of two zinc

Fig. 1. (a) Asymmetric unit of complex **1**·H₂O·ClO₄ with displacement ellipsoids drawn at the 25% probability level and hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity; (b) Optimized molecular structure of **1**, in methanol (Zn : Pale violet, N : Blue, O : Red, C : Grey. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity).

centers O4-Zn1-N1 and O5-Zn2-N3 are $171.15(15)^\circ$ and $168.83(16)^\circ$. The larger deviation from 180° is observed in Zn2 moiety preferred the square based pyramidal shape.

The Zn...Zn separation in the complex is 3.455 \AA . In the complex, one uncoordinated water molecule is also present per formula unit (Fig. 2).

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (\AA) and angles ($^\circ$) for $1 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{ClO}_4$ and selected optimized geometrical parameters of complex **1** in the ground (S_0) state at B3LYP levels in methanol

Bond length (\AA)					
Atoms (Zn1)	Solid state	Soln. state	Atoms (Zn2)	Solid state	Soln. state
Zn1-O1	1.968(3)	1.97832	Zn2-O2	2.024(3)	2.08980
Zn1-O2	2.023(3)	2.11592	Zn2-O3	1.999(3)	2.00004
Zn1-O4 ^a	2.121(5)	2.3341	Zn2-O5 ^a	2.063(4)	2.31819
Zn1-N1	2.131(4)	2.20961	Zn2-N3	2.116(4)	2.25998
Zn1-N2	2.113(4)	2.21772	Zn2-N4	2.114(4)	2.18427
Bond angle ($^\circ$)					
Atoms (Zn1)	Solid state	Soln. state	Atoms (Zn2)	Solid state	Soln. state
O1-Zn1-O2	110.37(13)	91.72021	O2-Zn2-O3	108.72(12)	107.83173
O1-Zn1-O4	92.49(16)	93.10121	O2-Zn2-O5	96.41(15)	118.64052
O1-Zn1-N1	94.91(15)	82.71606	O2-Zn2-N3	94.53(14)	85.33221
O1-Zn1-N2	126.28(17)	141.94705	O2-Zn2-N4	108.38(17)	103.18205
O2-Zn1-O4	89.38(17)	107.74585	O3-Zn2-O5	86.21(13)	76.82339
O2-Zn1-N1	92.57(14)	89.05625	O3-Zn2-N3	92.41(13)	79.68490
O2-Zn1-N2	123.34(16)	117.95413	O3-Zn2-N4	142.89(16)	139.34543
O4-Zn1-N1	171.15(15)	162.61440	O5-Zn2-N3	168.83(16)	143.91560
O4-Zn1-N2	87.80(18)	98.36814	O5-Zn2-N4	90.39(17)	103.18205
N1-Zn1-N2	83.92(17)	76.79879	N3-Zn2-N4	84.02(16)	77.29692

^aThe oxygen atom is coordinated water molecule.

Fig. 2. Packing diagram of complex $1 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{ClO}_4$ with hydrogen bonding and C-H... π (a) and π ... π stacking interactions (b).

The complex possesses several types of non-covalent interaction like inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonding (Table 3) and CH... π interaction. A unique ten member twist board ring is formed by the hydrogen bond between oxygen atom of non coordinated water molecule with oxygen atom coordinated water and phenoxo oxygen atom of the core moiety. This hydrogen bond cyclic ring is extended through oxygen atom of counter perchlorate anions (Fig. 2a). The CH... π and π ... π interactions are 3.023 and 3.546 Å (Fig. 2b). An extended 2D network perspective view was given in Electronic Supplementary Information Fig. S3.

Geometry optimization in solution phase and ground state structure analysis :

The geometry optimization of **1** was performed in solution phase (methanol) and their significant bond distances and angles of the optimized geometry at the ground S₀ state along with the crystal structure parameter are given in Table 2. The optimized structure in solution state was shown in Fig. 1b. In solution phase the geometry around the Zn1 atom is intermediate between square based pyramid and distorted trigonal bipyramid ($\tau = 0.34$) whereas that of Zn2 is square based pyramid ($\tau = 0.07$)³⁰. Hence in solution phase both the zinc center preferred the square based pyramidal environment while in solid state shows higher τ values. The crystal structure data in solid state are shown a regular deviation with optimized parameters in solution state. In each bond length some relaxation arises in solution phase which leads to larger bond distance and influence the bond angle as well as changes the geometrical environment around the zinc metal center. It was observed that the maximum deviation arises at Zn1-O4 and Zn2-O5 bond distance in solution phase.

The lengthening of bond distance of zinc ion with oxygen atom of coordinated water molecule in solution phase implies that the displacement of water molecule borne on adjacent metal centers come closer. The Zn...Zn separation of the complex in solution state was 3.201 Å, which implies that in solution state two zinc atoms come closer to each other rather than solid state (3.455).

Binding ability of H₃L towards cations by fluorometric study :

The emission intensity of H₃L in presence of various important metal ions were carried out in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/H₂O water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4 at room temperature (Fig. 3b). This study revealed the “turn-on” fluorescence nature of H₃L with Zn²⁺ ion whereas other transition metal ions including Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Cr³⁺ and Cd²⁺ did not induce emission intensity even at the higher concentration, rather they quenched the ligand emission intensity as there was a probability of an electron and energy transfer between the metal ion and ligand²⁴. When the experiment was carried out with ubiquitous intracellular metal ions such as K⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺ which exist at very high concentrations inside the cell, fluorescence intensity remained silent.

H₃L was used as a probe for metal-ion selectivity to examine whether it could be used as a selective sensor for Zn²⁺ in presence of other competitive cations found in biological systems. Emission spectra were measured for a 1 : 2 mixture of H₃L and Zn²⁺ in the presence of other metal ions. The prominent fluorescence enhancement observed upon mixing H₃L and Zn²⁺ remained unchanged, even in the presence of a 10-fold excess of metal ions such as K⁺, Na⁺, and Ca²⁺ (Fig. 3a, purple bar). This confirmed the excellent selectivity of H₃L for Zn⁺

Table 3. Hydrogen bonding parameters in **1**

Atoms	D-H(Å)	H...A (Å)	D-H...A (Å)	< D-H...A (°)	Symmetry
O1W...H1...O1	0.78(6)	2.05(6)	2.768(7)	152(6)	-x,1-y,1-z
O1W...H1...O7	0.83(10)	2.15(9)	2.906(8)	150(9)	1-x,1-y,2-z
O5...H5...O3	0.74(5)	1.97(5)	2.713(5)	175(6)	-x,1-y,1-z
O4...H4...O3	0.86(7)	1.90(6)	2.729(6)	161(6)	-
O4...H4...O1W	0.86(6)	1.97(6)	2.743(7)	149(6)	-x,1-y,1-z
O5...H5...O1	0.86(8)	1.86(8)	2.702(6)	165(6)	-
C18...H18B...O7	0.9700	2.5700	3.538(8)	173.00	-
C28...H28A...O4	0.9600	2.5400	3.093(9)	117.00	-
C31...H31A...O1W	0.9600	2.4900	3.423(10)	164.00	-

over other abundant cations in the cell. Notably, the fluorescence intensity of the zinc complex was partially quenched in the presence of 3d metal ions such as Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} and Cd^{2+} ions (Fig. 3a, purple bar). It is interesting to note that the fluorescence intensity of H_3L in the presence of Zn^{2+} is completely quenched in presence of Cu^{2+} which indicates that H_3L has a strong binding tendency towards Cu^{2+} metal ion. The binding constants are also calculated for these quencher metal ions using eq. (1)²⁵.

$$\log (F_0 - F)/F = \log K + n \log [M^{n+}] \quad (1)$$

Here F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensity from the fluorophore in the absence and the presence of different concentrations of M^{n+} ions respectively. The linear plot passing through the origin for $(F_0 - F)/F$ vs $[M^{n+}]^n$ (here $n = 2$; $a = 2/3$ and $M = \text{Cu}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cr}$ and Cd ; related figures are given in Supporting Information Fig. S4). From this, according to eq. (1), the values of K was estimated 1.15×10^{12} , 2.10×10^{11} , 1.66×10^{11} and $1.79 \times$

10^{11} M^{-2} respectively, for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cr^{3+} and Cd^{2+} towards H_3L . The binding constant value of the quencher metal ions towards the fluorophore, Cu^{2+} metal shows higher value.

Fluorogenic Zn^{2+} sensor :

In the fluorescence titration experiment, receptor H_3L was subjected to excitation at 280 nm and was monitored after each stepwise addition of Zn^{2+} ion to the solution in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4. The sensor showed weak emission probably because of quenching by the occurrence of a photo induced electron transfer (PET) process due to the presence of a lone pair of electrons of the donor atoms in the ligand (N, O donor)^{26c}. A gradual enhancement (~ 150 fold) of the fluorescence intensity was observed at 330 nm upon increasing the concentration of Zn^{2+} ions (Fig. 4). The reaction of Zn^{2+} with the chelating agent H_3L induced rigidity in the resulting molecule and produced a large CHEF effect which further induced the large enhance-

Fig. 3. (a) Histogram of metal-ion sensitivity and selectivity for H_3L in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4. Navy bars represent the fluorescence sensitivity of H_3L ($1 \mu\text{M}$) to various metal ions. Purple bars represent the fluorescence response measured after the addition of Zn^{2+} ($2 \mu\text{M}$) to the indicated metal ion- H_3L mixture. $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 290 \text{ nm}$; slit width 3/3; (b) Relative fluorescence intensity change of H_3L in the presence of various metal ions; (c) Photographs of chemo sensor H_3L in the presence of different metal ions under UV light.

ment of fluorescence^{26a,b}. Inset of Fig. 4b describes a plot of emission intensity at 330 nm against the titration of Zn²⁺ from 0 to 2.2 equivalents. It is clear from the plot that the fluorescence intensity reaches a plateau after addition of exactly 2.0 equivalents of Zn²⁺ ion and there is no significant enhancement of the fluorescence intensity on further addition of Zn²⁺ ion. This result strongly corroborates that the formation of 2 : 1 (M : L) complex in solution state. Assuming a 2 : 1 association between Zn²⁺ and H₃L, the binding constant is determined with the help of Benesi-Hildebrand equation is given as²⁷ :

$$(F_{\max} - F_0)/(F - F_0) = 1 + 1/K [\text{Zn}^{2+}]^2 \quad (2)$$

where, F_0 is the fluorescence of H₃L in the absence of externally added Zn²⁺, F is the fluorescence obtained at different [Zn²⁺] and F_{\max} is the fluorescence of H₃L at [Zn²⁺] in large excess. As shown in Fig. 4c, the plot of $\{(F_{\max} - F_0)/(F - F_0)\}$ vs $1/[\text{Zn}^{2+}]^2$ yields a straight line with slope = $(10.3 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-11}$, indicating that H₃L indeed associates with Zn²⁺ in a 1 : 2 stoichiometry. The intercept value 1.05 ± 0.5 , close to 1.0, also manifests the self-consistency of the experimental data. Therefore,

the ligand association constant K is reciprocal of slope, $9.87 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-2}$. The 1 : 2 complex formation in solution is further confirmed by ESI-MS⁺-(m/z) analysis (see Experimental section).

As shown in Fig. 4a, the fluorescence enhancement factor is measured at 330 nm and to the best of our knowledge this seems to be the highest value among the previously reported related Zn-sensors²⁸. So far the highest known fluorescence enhancement is 150 times that observed in the case of ZQ1 and ZQ2^{28b}. But both of them are very well known fluorescence sensor quinoline derivative and give emission band in visible region (400 nm to 800 nm). So far this is the first invented unique zinc sensor which enhanced the emission intensity not only by ~150 times but the band appears in UV region in both solution and solid state (in ESI Fig. S5).

The solid state emission band undergoes bathochromic shift (357 nm) during excitation due to different types of short interaction like CH- π and hydrogen bonding interaction (Fig. 2 and Table 3). In contrast, addition of other metal cations scarcely shows any fluorescence enhance-

Fig. 4. (a) Fluorescence titration of H₃L (1 μM) with gradual addition of Zn²⁺, 0–1.2 μM in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4; (b) Emission intensity at 330 nm vs [Zn²⁺]; (c) Shows linear plot for $\{(F_{\max} - F_0)/(F - F_0)\}$ vs $1/[\text{Zn}^{2+}]^2$. Slit width 3/3. $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 285 \text{ nm}$.

ment. So, the design of a highly selective and sensitive fluorescence sensor for Zn^{2+} detection without any interference from other metal ions, especially Cd^{2+} , is one of the most important objectives. The quantum yield determination of the zinc complex gave $\Phi = 0.399$, while the free ligand was found to be very weakly fluorescent. All these findings indicate that H_3L behaves as a highly sensitive fluorescent Zn^{2+} sensor.

Absorption spectral study of the complex :

A quantitative investigation of the binding affinity and mode of coordination of ligand with Zn^{2+} was studied by UV-Vis titration at 25 °C in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4. As shown in Fig. 5, describes a representative UV-Vis titration curve of H_3L with various concentration of Zn^{2+} ions. It has been observed that with increasing concentration of Zn^{2+} ion the absorption intensity of free ligand at 237 nm slightly increases while the intensity of absorption spectra at 280 nm gradually decreases with small blue shift and the absorption intensity at 290 nm gradually increases with two isosbestic points at 257 nm and 284 nm. It is to be noted that there is no changes of the absorption intensity both at 280 and 290 nm after the addition of excess of 2.0 equivalent of Zn^{2+} ion with respect to 1.0 equivalent of H_3L . This

result also corroborates with the formation of 2 : 1 (M : L) complex in solution.

To get better insight on experimental absorption values, TDDFT calculations were done for complex **1** on the basis of the optimized geometry. In order to analyze the nature of absorption, we performed an NTO analysis based on the calculated transition density matrices. Here we referred to the unoccupied and occupied NTOs as “electron” and “hole” transition orbitals. Based on our TDDFT NTOs analysis, the bands in the region 270–330 nm for this complex could be characterized as an ILCT states with some rearrangement of electron density over the ligand moiety. As illustrated in Fig. 6, optical excitations occurred from the occupied (hole) transition orbitals to the unoccupied (electron) transition orbitals. Hole NTOs contributing to the bands were localized on the π orbital of ligand while the electron NTOs were mainly delocalized over the π^* orbital of the ligand moiety. The absorption band at longer wavelength 290 nm for complex **1** consisted of two excitations. The excitations observed at energies were 4.2216 eV ($\lambda = 296$ nm and $f = 0.6145$) and 4.2637 eV ($\lambda = 290$ nm and $f = 0.4409$) and these are due to HOMO \rightarrow LUMO + 1 and HOMO – 1 \rightarrow LUMO + 1 transitions. As shown in Fig. 6, in

Fig. 5. (a) Absorption titration of H_3L (0.5 μM) with gradual addition of Zn^{2+} , 0.1–1.2 μM in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.2; (b) OD 288 nm vs $[\text{Zn}^{2+}]$; (c) Job's plot.

Fig. 6. Frontier molecular orbitals involved in the UV-Vis absorption of **1**.

HOMO and HOMO – 1 the electron density mainly resided at salicylaldehyde moiety but in the higher energy LUMO+ 1, the electron density localized at tertiary amine moiety. The theoretical spectrum of the complex **1** was given in Supporting Information Fig. S6.

Life time measurement :

The fluorescence lifetime measurements for the **H₃L** and **1** were carried out in methanol solution at room temperature with 280 nm excitation. The ligand shows mono exponential decay nature whereas the complex exhibits biexponential decay nature (Fig. 7). The average life time τ_f , ($\tau_f = \alpha_1\tau_1 + \alpha_2\tau_2$, where α_1 and α_2 are relative amplitudes of decay process) is used to compare the excited state stability of the complex and the value is found to be around 2 ns region (Table 4). The value of τ_1 life time of the complex is of similar order with the lifetime of corresponding ligand which reveals that in excited state the biexponential decay nature of the complex arises due to

Table 4. Photophysical parameters of the complex **1**·H₂O·ClO₄ and **H₃L**

	Φ	τ (ns)	τ_{avg} (ns)	$k_r \times 10^8$ (s ⁻¹)	$k_{\text{nr}} \times 10^9$ (s ⁻¹)
Complex 1	0.399	0.11, 4.5	1.89	2.1	3.1
H₃L	0.008	0.107	–	0.74	9.27

Fig. 7. Changes in the time-resolved photoluminescence decay of **H₃L** and **1**·H₂O·ClO₄ in methanol at room temperature obtained with 280 nm excitation.

the contribution of the ligand moiety and the complex itself. The radiative (k_r) and non radiative (k_{nr}) rate constants for both the complex and ligand are evaluated in Table 4. The smaller k_{nr} value as well as higher k_r value of the complex compared to that of the isolated ligand suggested the enhancement of fluorescence intensity due to complexation

Conclusion

In conclusion, a simple heptadentate N₄O₃ coordinating dinuclear zinc complex was synthesized. The sensor functioned as a “turn-on” fluorescence receptor only to Zn²⁺ ion in 3 : 2 v/v MeOH/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.2 at 25 °C. The increase in emission intensity approximately was 150 times in the presence of Zn²⁺ which accounted for the formation of a metal-ligand complex and could be used as zinc ion-selective luminescent probe, continuously emitting blue emission light in presence of UV lamp. Experimental results are corroborated by DFT and TDDFT analyses.

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Supplementary information

Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available : X-Ray crystallographic file in CIF format for **1**; Figs. S1-S6. CCDC reference number 1033742.

References

- (a) E. M. Nolan, J. Jaworski, K.-I. Okamoto, Y. Hayashi, M. Sheng and S. J. Lippard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 16812; (b) A. Hens, A. Maity and K. K. Rajak, *Inorg. Chimica Acta*, 2014, **423**, 408; (c) T. Koike, T. Abe, M. Takahashi, K. Ohtani, E. Kimura and M. Shiro, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 1764; (d) A. Hens and K. K. Rajak, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 44764.
- (a) A. Prasanna de Silva, H. Q. Nimal Gunaratne, T. Gunnlaugsson, A. J. M. Huxley, C. P. McCoy, J. T. Rademacher and T. E. Rice, *Chem. Rev.*, 1997, **97**, 1515; (b) A. Hens, P. Mondal and K. K. Rajak, *Dalton Trans.*, 2013, **42**, 14905.
- (a) A. Hens, P. Mondal and K. K. Rajak, *Polyhedron*, 2015, **85**, 255; (b) O. Reany, T. Gunnlaugsson and D. Parker, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 2000, 473; (c) A. Hens and K. K. Rajak, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 4219.
- J. M. Berg and Y. G. Shi, *Science*, 1996, **271**, 1081.
- C. J. Frederickson, E. J. Kasarskis, D. Ringo and R. E. Frederickson, *J. Neurosci. Methods*, 1987, **20**, 91.
- M. Taki, J. L. Wolford and T. V. O'Halloran, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 712.
- S. C. Burdette, C. J. Frederickson, W. Bu and S. J. Lippard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 1778.
- C. J. Chang, E. M. Nolan, J. Jaworski, K.-I. Okamoto, Y. Hayashi, M. Sheng and S. J. Lippard, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 6774.
- C. J. Chang, E. M. Nolan, J. Jaworski, S. C. Burdette, M. Sheng and S. J. Lippard, *Chem. Biol.*, 2004, **11**, 203.
- (a) T. Hirano, K. Kikuchi, Y. Urano and T. Nagano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 6555; (b) T. Hirano, K. Kikuchi, Y. Urano, T. Higuchi and T. Nagano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 12399.
- (a) E. M. Nolan, J. W. Ryu, J. Jaworski, R. P. Feazell, M. Sheng and S. J. Lippard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 15517; (b) K. Komatsu, K. Kikuchi, H. Kojima, Y. Urano and T. Nagano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 10197; (c) S. Aoki, D. Kagata, M. Shiro, K. Takeda and E. Kimura, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 13377.
- E. Runge and E. K. U. Gross, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1984, **52**, 997.
- (a) A. D. Becke, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 5648; (b) C. Lee, W. Yang and R. G. Parr, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1988, **37**, 785.
- (a) M. E. Casida, C. Jamoroski, K. C. Casida and D. R. Salahub, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **108**, 4439; (b) R. E. Stratmann, G. E. Scuseria and M. J. Frisch, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **109**, 8218; (c) R. Bauernschmitt and R. Ahlrichs, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1996, **256**, 454.
- (a) V. Barone and M. Cossi, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 1998, **102**, 1995; (b) M. Cossi and V. Barone, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2001, **115**, 4708; (c) M. Cossi, N. Rega, G. Scalmani and V. Barone, *J. Comp. Chem.*, 2003, **24**, 669.
- P. J. Hay and W. R. Wadt, *J. Chem Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 299.
- M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Caricato, X. Li, H. P. Hratchian, A. F. Izmaylov, J. Bloino, G. Zheng, J. L. Sonnenberg, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. Brothers, K. N. Kudin, V. N. Staroverov, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, N. Rega, J. M. Millam, M. Klene, J. E. Knox, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, R. L. Martin, K. Morokuma, V. G. Zakrzewski, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, Ö. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, J. Cioslowski and D. J. Fox, Gaussian 09, (Revision A.1), Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford, CT, 2009.
- (a) N. M. O'Boyle, A. L. Tenderholt and K. M. Langner, *J. Comp. Chem.*, 2008, **29**, 839; (b) J. W. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81; (c) K. Wolniski, J. F. Hilton and P. Pulay, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 8251.
- SMART; SAINT; SADABS; XPREP; SHELXTL, Bruker AXS Inc., Madison, WI, 1998.
- G. M. Sheldrick, SHELXTL, v. 6.14, Bruker AXS Inc., Madison, WI, 2003.
- (a) C. K. Johnson, ORTEP Report ORNL-5138, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN, 1976; (b) C. F. Macrae, P. R. Edgington, P. McCabe, E. Pidcock, G. P. Shields, R. Taylor, M. Towler and J. van de Streek, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, 2006, **39**, 453.
- (a) A. Mondal, S. Sarkar, D. Chopra, T. N. Guru Row, K. Pramanik and K. K. Rajak, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 703.
- C. O'Sullivan, G. Murphy, B. Murphy and B. Hathaway, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1999, 1835.

Hens *et al.* : Blue emissive Zn^{II} sensor by N₄O₃ heptadentate ligand in mixed aqueous solution *etc.*

24. A. Hens, P. Mondal and K. K. Rajak, *Dalton Trans.*, 2013, **42**, 14905.
25. (a) X. Z. Feng, Z. Lin, L. J. Yang, C. Wang and C. L. Bai, *Talanta*, 1998 **47**, 1223; (b) L. Gelamo and M. Tabak, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2000 **A56**, 2255.
26. (a) T. Harano, K. Kikuchi, Y. Urano and T. Nagano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 6555; (b) S. C. Burdette and S. J. Lippard, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2001, **216**, 333; (c) D. Das, B. G. Chand, K. K. Sarker, J. Dinda and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2006, **25**, 2333.
27. (a) A. Mallick and N. Chattopadhyay, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 2005, **81**, 419; (b) H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703; (c) N. J. Turro, "Modern Molecular Photochemistry", Benjamin Cummings Publishing Co., Inc, Menlo Park, CA, 1978.
28. (a) L. M. T. Canzoniero, D. M. Turetsky and D. W. Choi, *J. Neurosci.*, 1999, **19 RC31**, 1; (b) E. M. Nolan, J. Jaworski, K.-I. Okamoto, Y. Hayashi, M. Sheng and S. J. Lippard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 16812; (c) P. Roy, K. Dhara, M. Manassero, J. Ratha and P. Banerjee, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 6405; (d) Y. Mikata, M. Wakamatsu, A. Kawamura, N. Yamanaka, S. Yano, A. Odani, K. Morihira and S. Tamotsu, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 9262; (e) E. M. Nolan, J. Jaworski, M. E. Racine, M. Sheng and S. J. Lippard, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 9748; (f) N. C. Lim, J. V. Schuster, M. C. Porto, M. A. Tanundra, L. Yao, H. C. Freake and C. Brckner, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 2018; (g) E. M. Nolan and S. J. Lippard, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 8310; (h) E. M. Nolan, S. C. Burdette, J. H. Harvey, S. A. Hilderbrand and S. J. Lippard, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 2624; (i) K. Komatsu, Y. Urano, H. Kojima and T. Nagano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 13447; (j) K. R. Gee, Z.-L. Zhou, W.-J. Qian and R. Kennedy, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 776; (k) S. C. Burdette, G. K. Walkup, B. Spingler, R. Y. Tsien and S. J. Lippard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 7831; (l) H. A. Godwin and J. M. Berg, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 6514; (m) Y. Liu, N. Zhang, Y. Chen and L. H. Wang, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 315; (n) E. Tomat and S. J. Lippard, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 9113; (o) Y.-M. Li, J. Shi, X. Wu, Z.-F. Luo, F.-L. Wang and Q.-X. Guo, *Cell Biochem. Funct.*, 2009, **27**, 417; (p) Z. Xu, K.-H. Baek, H. N. Kim, J. Cui, X. Qian, D. R. Spring, I. Shin and J. V. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 601; (q) A. R. Lippert, E. J. New and C. J. Chang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 10078.

